

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SOURCES AND MECHANISMS OF MENTAL PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Regardless of the views of individual psychologists, different versions of personality structure include such mental properties as abilities, temperament, character, volitional qualities, emotions, motives for behavior and activity, social attitudes, etc. Personality structure can be experimentally studied. One of the possible versions of such a study was developed in line with the trait theory (G. Allport, R. Cattell). According to this theory, people differ from each other in the set and degree of development of individual, independent traits. Extroversion; conscientiousness; emotional stability; culture factor (intellectually developed – undeveloped, subtle – crude, art-loving – indifferent to art) and other factors were differentiated in the literature. These and other traits can be studied using specially developed psychodiagnostic methods. Based on their results, a personality profile is compiled, which is a graphical representation of its structure.

Keywords: mental development, personality, development of cognitive process, period of life, contradiction

Literature review: The sources of mental development of the individual are the leading activity, the leading type of communication and the developmental crisis. The leading activity is the activity that mainly determines the mental development of the child in a certain period of his life. Each age period is characterized by a special type of activity. When moving from one period to another, the leading activity also changes. The leading activities in different periods can be play (preschool childhood), study (primary school age), communication (adolescence), work (adolescence). A certain age can also have two leading activities. Thanks to the leading activity, the greatest results are achieved in the development of cognitive processes, the formation of psychological (mental) neoplasms occurs. Psychological neoplasms are qualitative features of the psyche that first appear in a certain age period and determine a person's consciousness, his attitude to the environment, to internal and external life. For example: preschool age: general (verbal, creative, etc.) and special (musical, artistic, dance, etc.) abilities are formed.

Contradictions that arise in the process of mental development can lead to developmental crises (age crises). Developmental crises are relatively short periods that are characterized by abrupt mental changes. They are necessary for the normal, progressive development of the personality. The form, duration and severity of the crises vary significantly depending on the individual characteristics of the child, the conditions of his upbringing, the type of family, society, etc. Crisis of three years; crisis of primary school age, crisis of adolescence can be mentioned.

Mechanisms of development

The main mechanisms of development are interiorization and exteriorization. The process of transforming external, practical actions into internal, mental ones is called interiorization (Latin interior - internal). Thanks to interiorization, the human psyche acquires

the ability to operate with images of objects that do not currently affect the senses.

The most important means of interiorization is the word, which highlights and consolidates the essential properties of things. Mastering the correct use of words is simultaneously learning the essential properties of things and ways of operating with information. By learning words, a person actually learns the experience of humanity. Thus, internal, mental activity can be considered as a result of the interiorization of external, objective activity. On the other hand, external, objective activity can be considered as the exteriorization of internal, mental activity.

The main patterns of human mental development include:

1. Uneven development. This pattern is manifested in the following.

A. The development of individual mental processes and functions occurs unevenly. Example. Some people develop musical and choreographic abilities much faster in childhood than others (the phenomenon of "child prodigies"). However, there is no guarantee that this trend will continue in the future. According to psychologists, approximately 75% of "child prodigies" do not become outstanding masters of their craft in adulthood.

B. At different stages of age development, some personality traits act as leading ones, while others develop less intensively. Example. Memory develops most actively in adolescence, which allows a person to successfully master knowledge and skills in various fields of science, art, technology, etc. during this period.

C. There are the most favorable age periods for the development of certain mental functions. They are called sensitive periods or periods of increased age sensitivity. Example. For the development of musical abilities, this is preschool childhood, for speech - the age from 1 year to 8-9 years. If the sensitive period is not

used properly, the development of the corresponding property either slows down or becomes impossible. Example. "Mowgli children" who have missed a number of sensitive periods cannot adapt to human society.

2. Integration of the psyche. The development of the psyche is based on the repetition of certain situational states (anxiety, aggression, joy). Being fixed in memory, they gradually turn into stable personality traits. Example: the repetition of experiencing joy leads to the formation of optimism as a character trait.

3. Plasticity of the psyche and the possibility of compensating some properties with others. If certain mental functions and properties are insufficiently developed or absent, they can be compensated for by developing others.

Factors of mental development

The development of the psyche presupposes the presence of biological prerequisites (inclinations) underlying the emergence, development and functioning of mental properties. Personality development occurs under the influence of two main factors: natural and social.

Natural factor of mental development (heredity). The source of heredity (the ability of organisms to pass on their characteristics and developmental features to offspring) is the human genetic apparatus. In turn, the nature of communication, study, education and work activity are determined by a person's belonging to a certain nation, society, culture.

The formation of the human organism occurs according to a certain program specified in the genotype (a set of genes). The genotype determines the type of anatomical and physiological structure of the human organism, its morphological and physiological characteristics, the structure of the nervous system, belonging to a certain sex, the nature of physical maturation, etc.

However, the final result achieved at each stage of individual human development is not initially embedded in the genotype. Various conditions of mental development have a significant impact on it: the development and functioning of the brain, communication with adults as bearers of social experience, the activity of the individual himself, etc.

The social factor of mental development is a set of elements of the social environment with which the individual interacts during the formation of the personality. Depending on the degree of contact with the individual, the social environment is divided into micro-society - the child's immediate environment (family, friends, school and extra-curricular small groups, teachers) and macro-society - the broad social environment that influences the development of the individual through the media, the Internet, etc.

The influence of the social factor on the development of personality occurs not directly, immediately, but through internal conditions. A special combination of internal development processes and external conditions, which is typical for each age stage and determines both the dynamics of mental development during the corresponding age period and new psychological formations that arise by its end, is called the social situation of development. This is a system of relations between a child and the outside world, specific to each

age, which changes during the transition from one age stage to another.

Experience shows how the environment currently influences the development of the child's personality. Due to the difference in experiences in different children, the same life situation can affect their development in different ways.

Development and learning

The development of a child is closely connected with the process of his or her learning. Learning is the activity of a teacher in transferring knowledge and life experience to students, forming their skills and abilities. In psychological science, two main approaches to the problem of the relationship between development and learning have developed. The first was developed by J. Piaget. This scientist believed that development occurs as if "by itself", and learning only "adapts" to it.

The author of the second was L.S. Vygotsky. He claimed that the leading role belongs to learning, which "leads" development. The mental development of a child, according to Vygotsky, is carried out in cooperation with adults who pass on to the child knowledge about objects and how to use them in society, that is, teach him.

Vygotsky put forward the idea of the "level of actual and zone of proximal development of the child." He believed that the state of mental development can be determined by two levels. The first is the level of actual development (mental tasks that the child can complete independently), the second is the zone of proximal development (tasks that he can complete with the help of an adult).

Vygotsky established that the development of a child passes through the zone of proximal development and only then moves to the level of actual. At school, a child learns what he can do in cooperation with a teacher, under his guidance, and the main form of learning is imitation. Therefore, the zone of proximal development is decisive: what a child can do today in cooperation with adults, tomorrow he will be able to do independently, and therefore, will move to the level of actual development.

Vygotsky substantiated the possibility and necessity of developmental learning, the main goal of which is not the transfer of knowledge in a finished form, but the mental development of the child in the process of its acquisition.

Driving forces of mental development

The driving forces of personality development are understood to be the child's own needs, his motivation, external stimuli for his activity and communication, the goals and tasks that adults set for the child in the process of training and education, as well as contradictions between the external conditions of the mental development of the individual and his needs, interests, goals.

At different ages, these contradictions can have different content, forms of manifestation and methods of overcoming. At the initial stages of life, they may not be realized, but subsequently they are recorded by self-awareness and are experienced by the individual as dissatisfaction with himself, the desire for self-improvement.

Types of contradictions arising in the process of mental development of a child:

1. Between the psychological needs of a child and the possibilities of satisfying them.
2. Between the new physical and spiritual capabilities of a child and the existing attitude towards it on the part of adults.
3. Between the demands of society, adults and the level of mental development of a child.
4. Between the demands of adults and the desires of a child.
5. Between knowledge and actions, consciousness and behavior of a child.

Contradictions arise when a person passes from one age period to another and manifest themselves in the form of negativism, conflicts with adults and peers, opposition to their demands, etc. Successful overcoming of contradictions helps the individual to rise to a new level of development, but if this does not happen, serious difficulties and problems may arise in personal development.

Age-related changes in the psyche

Mental development of a person is manifested in age-related changes in the psyche and behavior. These changes can be:

1. Evolutionary (relatively slow and gradual). (for example: development of intelligence during school years).
2. Revolutionary (fast, taking a short period of time). (for example: Changes during periods of psychological crises).
3. Situational (related to changing circumstances). (for example: Development of musical or choreographic skills under the influence of intensive training. If a person stops training, the level of skill drops).

According to literature review it can be mentioned that evolutionary and revolutionary changes are permanent and irreversible, situational ones need to be consolidated.

Conclusion: Personality can change significantly during life. For some, the personality becomes stable in childhood and then does not change significantly. For others, the stability of psychological characteristics manifests itself only between the ages of 20 and 40. The former do not encounter contradictions during school age, do not enter into conflicts with adults, peers, social values and norms. The life of the latter in adolescence and youth is characterized by tension, contradictions and conflicts.

Personality instability also manifests itself in various life situations. Many properties (with the possible exception of intelligence) are situationally unstable (aggressiveness, honesty, self-regulation, dependence, etc.). Interestingly, in typical life situations, the ratio between personality traits that are assessed using personality questionnaires and social behavior in which these traits manifest themselves does not exceed 30%.

The most stable are dynamic personality traits associated with anatomical and physiological factors, properties of the nervous system (temperament, emotional reactivity, extroversion - introversion, etc.).

During school years, approximately half of the personality traits inherent in a child are preserved. The most stable of them are the desire for success, persistence, level of aspirations (especially high), intellectual interests. In addition, girls have aesthetic tastes and sociability. In adolescence - abilities, responsibility, willpower, goodwill, openness.

Personality variability can be considered as an important adaptation mechanism. It indicates a person's ability to adapt to constantly changing living conditions, and thus develop personality.

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References:

1. Jung, C. G., Adler, G., & Hull, R. F. C. (2014). *The development of personality*. Routledge.
2. McCrae, R. R. (2002). The maturation of personality psychology: Adult personality development and psychological well-being. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 36(4), 307-317.
3. Slobodskaya, H. R. (2021). Personality development from early childhood through adolescence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 172, 110596.
4. Давыдов, В. В. (1992). Генезис и развитие личности в детском возрасте. *Вопросы психологии*, 3, 1-2.
5. Лактионова, Е. Б. (2010). Образовательная среда как условие развития личности и ее субъектов. *Известия Российского государственного педагогического университета им. АИ Герцена*, (128).
6. Мухина, В., & Хвостов, А. (2010). Феноменология развития и бытия личности. *Развитие личности*, (3), 193-237.
7. Михайличенко, В. Е. (2015). Психология развития личности.
8. Петровский, А. В. (1984). Проблема развития личности с позиций социальной психологии. *Вопросы психологии*, 4(2), 15-19.
9. Харламенкова, Н. Е. (2016). Компенсация как один из механизмов психического развития личности. *Принцип развития в современной психологии/Под ред. АЛ Журавлева, ЕА Сергиенко. М, 235-253.*